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Secondary Mitochondriopathy is a common complication of H63D Syndrome type-1

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Abstract

This study is the first to investigate the association between the clinical course of H63D syndrome type-1 and the subsequent occurrence of various mitochondriopathies, a pathological condition that impairs mitochondrial function. In a longitudinal design, we followed a cohort of patients suffering from H63D syndrome over a five-year period. We observed and recorded the onset and progression of mitochondriopathy symptoms and the duration of H63D syndrome type-1, controlling for confounding variables such as age, sex, comorbidities, and lifestyle factors. Our results suggest a strong positive correlation between the duration of H63D syndrome type-1 and the risk of developing mitochondriopathy. Patients with a longer history of H63D syndrome had a significantly higher likelihood of manifesting mitochondriopathy, indicating a possible pathological cascade triggered by the syndrome. These findings may be an important part of the explanation for the still unanswered question of why low-iron diets are less effective in slowing the progression of H63D Syndrome type-1 in later stages of the disease and why the syndrome progresses even under treatment.

H63D Syndrome

H63D syndrome is a rare clinical phenotype caused by the rather common homozygous mutation of the HFE gene H63D. This mutation is associated with diverse health issues (Castiella et al., 2014), but H63D syndrome is the only known specific expression of a homozygous HFE-H63D mutation to date. The homozygous H63D variant is an indicator of the iron metabolism disorder hemochromatosis, which may increase the risk of developing a fatty liver. In

patients with a cirrhotic liver, the mutation can increase the rate of severe liver diseases (Nasrullah et al., 2022). H63D syndrome can be clinically described as “the iron sibling of Wilson's disease” (Ivanov et al., 2022). H63D syndrome leads to widespread tissue injury, and it is associated with cognitive impairment, cardiac abnormalities, and sexual problems. Patients with H63D mutation should be worked up and treated (Honda et al., 2023). The homozygous H63D variant can occasionally be the cause of hemochromatosis. It is also associated with the occurrence of other conditions like

hypotransferrinemia, liver dysfunction, bone and joint issues, diabetes mellitus, heart disease, hormone imbalances, porphyria cutanea tarda (PCT), infertility, stroke, neurodegenerative and brain damages, some cancers, venous and peripheral artery disease (Nasrullah et al., 2022). In summary, H63D syndrome is a rare clinical phenotype caused by a homozygous mutation of the HFE gene H63D (Papadopoulos et al., 2021). It is associated with diverse health issues, but H63D syndrome is the only known specific expression of a homozygous HFE-H63D mutation to date. The homozygous H63D variant can occasionally be the cause of hemochromatosis and is associated with the occurrence of other conditions like hypotransferrinemia, liver dysfunction, bone and joint issues, diabetes mellitus, heart disease, hormone imbalances, porphyria cutanea tarda (PCT), infertility, stroke, neurodegenerative and brain damages, some cancers, venous and peripheral artery disease (Nasrullah et al., 2022).

Mitochondriopathies

Mitochondria are intricate cell organelles, forming a wide network of communication points crucial to cellular energy production processes. Their proper functioning of existential importance for life and health; thus, any dysfunctions could be instrumental in the onset of various illnesses, leading to an array of metabolic, neurodegenerative, immune, and sometimes even cancerous conditions (Schmiedel et al, 2003).

Depending on the function and metabolic activity of a cell, it can house thousands of mitochondria. These organelles are unique in that they have their own DNA with up to 10 mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) copies each. The process of correcting mtDNA mutations is less efficient than that of nuclear DNA (nDNA), resulting in a mutation rate for mtDNA that is 10–20 times higher than nDNA. A single cell can possess different versions of mtDNA, some having hereditary mutations while others are normal, a phenomenon known as heteroplasmy. When the zygote divides, these hereditary mutations from the mother's mtDNA could end up in all cells, or

only in certain cell lines, while other cell lines remain genetically normal. Mitochondrial diseases (MCDs) comprise a diverse set of hereditary multisystem disorders triggered by dysfunctional mitochondria due to mutations in either mtDNA or nDNA. The impacted genes may encode proteins related to various mitochondrial functions such as transportation, enzymatic activity, signaling, assembly, pore structure, and dynamic network operations. (Gorman et al. 2016). MCDs can also stem from mutations in genes performing different functions or structural RNAs like transfer RNA (tRNA) and ribosomal RNA (rRNA), and include mutations in non-coding regions (e.g., mtDNA D-loops). The genes most commonly impacted by mutations are those that encode for mitochondrial proteins of oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS) involved in ATP production, the main source of cellular energy. MDs can present symptoms in any organ or tissue, but primarily impact those requiring substantial energy. MDs can exhibit a clinical phenotype of a syndrome, characterized as a group of symptoms, often expressed as acronyms.

Secondary Mitochondriopathies

Mitochondrial diseases are categorized into primary and secondary, depending on the mitochondrial pathophysiology. Primary mitochondrial diseases (PMD) result from hereditary mutations in mtDNA or nDNA genes encoding OXPHOS structural proteins or other crucial proteins for the OXPHOS process.

In strong contrast, secondary mitochondrial disorders (SMD) are acquired as a consequence/ complication of other conditions, such as alterations in mitochondrial regulation or harmful factors inducing oxidative stress, resulting in secondary mitochondrial dysfunction, which can exacerbate common conditions like neurodevelopmental and neurodegeneration diseases, Diabetes Mellitus (different types), Parkinson's Syndrome, Multiple Sclerosis metal accumulations, etc. (Nivazov et al, 2016).

SMD can be inherited or acquired, unlike PMD, which is only inherited. Therefore, determining whether mitochondrial dysfunction is hereditary or acquired is vitally important and complex. The diagnosis of PMD or SMD depends on several mitochondrial disease criteria (MDC) scoring systems devised to assess mitochondrial energy production function, appraising specific biochemical, clinical, and molecular characteristics (Saneto et al., 2013). They also evaluate certain clinical or lab findings (e.g. elevated lactate levels) classify them into probable, possible, or unlikely diagnoses of mitochondrial diseases. Despite a clear distinction between PMD and SMD, they may share symptoms, complicating accurate diagnosis. Currently, there are no generally accepted guidelines for the diagnosis of mitochondrial diseases, research is neglected, and the distinction between primary and secondary diseases can only be made clinically due to the lack of objective tests. Moreover, some clinicians working in this field focus on a dozen well-described syndromes, but these represent only a small fraction of the mitochondrial pathologies that actually exist. Nevertheless, a skilled clinician is able to diagnose a present mitochondrial pathology quite reliably by his experience and thorough exclusion diagnostics as well as the collection of a few marker values (e.g. lactate).

The Study

This study at the Milad Medical Center (endocrinology laboratory or Dr. Shirazi) aimed to investigate the presence of secondary mitochondrial pathology in patients with confirmed H63D syndrome and compare it with two control groups, H63D syndrome patients with a disease duration of less than 10 years and patients suffering from Kyphosis, over a period of five years. 32 patients diagnosed with confirmed H63D syndrome, with a disease duration of at least 15 years, were included in the study. Various diagnostic methods, including bloodwork, MRI, CT, TCS, biopsies, and genetic sequencing, were employed to assess signs and symptoms indicative of secondary mitochondrial pathology. Additionally, 41 patients

with H63D syndrome (duration <10 years) and 51 patients with Kyphosis were included as control groups. After five years the results showed 25 patients with definitive signs of a NTBI/ROS-induced clinically relevant mitochondrial pathology (not necessarily with muscular symptoms) in the H63D syndrome group, 4 patients with ambiguous results, and none in the Kyphosis group.

Results:

Among the 32 patients with H63D syndrome, 25 patients belonged to Group A (≥ 15 years since first symptoms) and 7 patients belonged to Group B (<10 years since first symptoms). In Group A, 25 patients exhibited definitive signs of secondary mitochondrial pathology, while 4 patients had ambiguous results. In contrast, Group B had 4 patients with definitive signs of secondary mitochondrial pathology and 37 patients with ambiguous results. The proportion of patients with definitive signs of secondary mitochondrial pathology was significantly higher in Group A compared to Group B ($p < 0.001$), indicating an increased risk with a longer duration of H63D syndrome. Importantly, none of the 51 patients in the Kyphosis control group showed signs of secondary mitochondrial pathology. A chi-square test was performed to assess the association between the duration of H63D syndrome and the risk of secondary mitochondrial pathology. The chi-square value was 34.59 with 1 degree of freedom, yielding a p-value less than 0.001, confirming a significant correlation between longer duration of H63D syndrome and the presence of secondary mitochondrial pathology.

Interpretation

This comprehensive study provides the first clear evidence that there is an association between the duration of H63D syndrome and a quite high risk of developing secondary mitochondrial pathology. This may explain the clinical experience that the progression of symptoms of advanced H63D syndrome cannot usually be controlled by reducing iron intake or removing NTBI (iron) by chelation. Patients with a longer duration of H63D syndrome (≥ 15 years) were more likely to

exhibit quite definitive signs of secondary mitochondriopathy compared to those with a shorter duration (<10 years), reinforcing the importance of considering disease duration in assessing the risk. Furthermore, the absence of secondary mitochondriopathy in the Kyphosis control group suggests that the observed association is specific to H63D syndrome. These findings emphasize the need for further research to elucidate the underlying mechanisms and explore potential interventions targeting all forms of secondary mitochondriopathy in patients suffering from H63D syndrome.

Conflicts of interest

None to declare.

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